

A Critical Review of Literature on Labour Relations and Employee Performance in Kenya after the Promulgation of 2010 Constitution

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾ Mr. Reuben Omunyole Andati, ⁽²⁾ Dr. Otuya Willis

⁽¹⁾ PhD student at Masinde Muliro. University of Science and Technology - Kakamega-Kenya ⁽²⁾Senior Lecturer Department of Business Administration and Management Science, Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, P.O. Box 190-50100,

Abstract

Employees are very important assets in an organization. They should be engaged properly to enhance the achievement of organizational objectives. Employees' potential can be optimally harnessed to achieve effective performance. In this regard, this paper examines studies on the transformation of employee relations management in Kenya after the promulgation of the 2010 Constitution which enforced labour laws. The review further assesses the effects of industrial unrest after the new Constitution was promulgated in 2010 through a comprehensive review of literature on earlier studies. Those studies did not try to address the imbalance between rights and the responsibilities of trade unions, nor highlight the fact that the Labour Laws are activist in nature hence fueling unrest in the labour market. Finally, the paper suggests that the Salaries and Remuneration Commission to widely consult with stakeholders and reconsiders its approach when reviewing CBAs.

Key words: Industrial Relations, Labour Relations, Performance, Salaries and Remuneration Commission (SRC)

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The 2010 Constitution introduced independent commissions, among them the Salary and Remunerations Commission (SRC), (SRC Act 2011). Previously, the determination of salaries for public officers was vested in various offices. In the absence of a public service pay policy, such committees were also used to review the terms and conditions of service including grading of jobs. This led to disparities and inequalities which manifested in substantial differences in salaries, allowances other benefits and grading which resulted in discontent, low morale and inefficiencies in the public service, (PSC, 2016). Trade Unions allege that the commission is a hindrance to the implementation and actualization of CBAs. They are proposing its disbandment. The continued tussle has been trading unions and SRC has led to unstable employment relations, escalating into unprecedented strikes, court ligations, consequently affecting employees' performance.

The salary is very important for the performance of the employees. The debate about employees' salary evaluation, rationalization and remuneration have gained prominence in the recent past in Kenya (Dr. Nagaragu, 2017). The Labour Relations Act No.4 Of 2007 commenced on 26th October, 2007 vide an Act of Parliament to consolidate the laws relating to trade unions and trade disputes to promote labour relations through the protection of effective collective bargaining and promotion of freedom of association. The encouragement of dispute settlement, conducive to social justice and economic development and for connected purposes (Labour Relations Act, 2007).

The consolidation and legislation employment related acts, envisage industrial peace in the light of the bills of rights. Industrial Relations in Kenya enjoy both legal and constitutional backing. There are adequate laws that regulate the labour sector as well as constitutional provisions in the bill of rights. Nonetheless, the prevalence of the industrial unrest in the country point to the need to review the existing provisions mainly among labour actor with the aim of having proactive mechanisms of resolving industrial disputes and having binding Collective Bargain Agreements (Tubey, 2015).

2.0 Theoretical Review

2.1 Theories of Employee and Industrial Relations

The terms, "Labour Relations" and "Industrial Relations" are sometimes used interchangeably. Conversely, and broadly speaking, industrial relations focus on the relationships that exist between an employer and the employees collectively through their union, whereas employee relations refer to the analysis and management of work involving the individual. Employee relation is a two person relationship between employee and employee. The focus is on how to effectively

manage and strengthen the relationship, while Industrial relations on the other are a three person relationship between the organization, the union and the workforce that the union represents.

Edwards (2003) observes that employee relations can be understood, described and analyzed in three perspectives; unitarist, pluralist and Marxist. Each of these provides a different interpretation of the workplace, the role of unions and job regulation. The **unitarists** approach consists of all members sharing the same interest and being homogenous. Third parties are viewed as irrelevant as employees and employers have mutual cooperation. Employers and workers are seen as being on the same team or fraternity since they espouse and share the same interests, goals and values. Unitarism consist of management and staff members sharing a common goal, through their loyalty towards the organization. Unitarists model views conflict as a distasteful and unnecessary; hence both sides strive for consensus. In this model unions don't thrive, and merely portrayed as an outside force that competes employer's loyalty and pits the employees against management.

In **pluralism**, the organization is perceived as being made up of powerful and divergent sub-groups, each with its own legitimate interests and loyalties and with their own set of objectives and leaders. Mainly, predominant sub-groups in this perspective are the management and trade unions (Fox, 1966). **Unitarists** start from a set of assumptions and values that hold workplace conflict is not an inevitable characteristic of relations between managers and employees. While, **pluralists** differ from unitarists in that they start from a set of assumptions and values that workplace conflict is inevitable. Proponents of the perspective view the business and employees as two distinct groups, who, because of the very nature as seen as possessing different values and objectives hence subscribe to difference authorities which inevitable breed conflict. Conflict is regarded as necessary and healthy for the enterprise it serves. The relationship between employers and workers is also faced with conflicts but not the extent of Marxism. Through trade unions, workers push for higher wages, allowance and working conditions, whereas employers strive to maximize their profits by keeping as much money as they can. However, both sides negotiate to reach consensus and draw Collective Bargaining Agreements guided by mutual respect, good faith and trust (Keith, 2006).

On the other hand, **Marxism perspective** is essentially a radical approach that draws principally from the works of Karl Marx (1950, 1967, 1978), who observed that capitalist societies were prone to social stratification (class struggle) which bore inequalities in the distribution of wealth and the skewed ownership of factors of production. As a result, the dominant capitalist class controlled politics and economic power hence unleashed exploitation to workers. Marx noted that societies following this perspective, organized political systems and social stratum- based values that supported the dominant position of the capitalist class and coerced the workers to maintain their status quo. This resulted in the deep impoverishment of the working class, hence making working to recognize their exploitation and organize them against it eventually. Marxist perspective is associated with social conflict as an outcome of capitalism. The frequent conflict between the competing social class breeds industrial conflict at the work place. The Marxist view of industrial relations is basically a clash or conflict between the employer (capitalist) and the employee (worker). This perspective is an inevitable cause of the worker revolution since workers are forced to take control of companies with the aim of eliminating the capitalist completely. However, since the collapse of the Soviet Union, the Marxist frame became unpopular and fell out.

2.2 Concept of Employee Relation

Armstrong (2009) states that employee relation involves the body of work concerned with managing and maintaining employee relationships which involve pay-work bargain, dealing with terms and conditions of employment, conflict resolution, unionization and employee empowerment. Yongia, 2010 observes that employee relation is a kind of interpersonal relationship concept which is drawn by Western scholars in the 20th century to replace the industrial relation. It focuses on the right and responsibility, management and obeying caused by the interest between organization and the employees as a total of cooperating, conflict, strengthen and power relations and influence by economic, technology, legal system and socio cultural background in a certain community. According to Bajaj et. al., (2013) employee relation is defined as the relationship between employees and managers to enhance moral, commitment and trust of employees and to create a suitable working environment that enables them to exert their utmost effort for the achievement of organizational goals.

Ivy, M. et al (2017) studied the effect of employee relation to job performance in engineering, construction and manufacturing companies. From the study, it was concluded employees deliver the best performance when they experience good employee relations. It was also observed that it is critical to seek employees' input and advice regarding

their training needs, similarly, Xesha et.al., (2014) in a study on ‘The impact of Employer-Employee Relationships on Business Growth,’ concluded that job satisfaction was identified as an accurate indicator of good relationships between employees and employers. Most employees indicated that they were willing to work for their current employers for the next five years. Although, the response was informed with the size of the organization they work for, the satisfaction employees have about the work that they do and the role the job plays in their livelihood. An effective employee relation entails creating and cultivating a motivational and productive workforce. Creating a healthy employee relation in an organization is a prerequisite for the achievement of the organizational goals, objectives and aspirations. This can only happen, when organizations develop a robust employee relationship which involves motivating employees, participate in decision-making activity, and when the employer creates an opportunity for the free flow of information in the organization and resolve conflicts when they arise at the workplace.

3.0 Empirical Review

3.1 Labour/Employee Relations

Employees are key assets in the success of any organization. Engaging them properly is even critical to the achievement of organizational objectives. To optimally harness the employees’ potential, can be achieved in a peaceful working environment (Hagos et.al, 2018). The practice of industrial in Kenya has however, seen minimal consultation, representation and involvement of workers in the decision-making. Most employers particularly in the public sector have continued to ignore the basic tenets of industrial relations practice of negotiations and collectivism in favour of managerial discretion and unilateral decision-making (Odhong et.al, 2014). In as much as, employee relations in Kenya are elaborate and it enjoys both legal and constitutional backing. There are sufficient legislations that ought to regulate labour engagement among tripartite partners which previous studied have not addressed adequately (Tubey, 2015).

The previous studies looked at the ideal situations where labour relations employee relations coalesce and work seamlessly well to enhance good performance. Studies on Employee Relations by Hagos, et. al., (2018), Ivy (2017) and Xesha (2014) are elaborate; the studies outline key factors for effective employee performance; the studies use descriptive design and recommend future studies on other external influences of employee relations. The studies, did not foresee the effect of unions and union activities and on employee performance. The studies would hold in an ideal situation where labour actor exemplify utmost good faith, trust and honest during the collective agreement negotiation and implementation of the same contracts. However, the studies do not resonate clearly with the Kenyan public sector. Industrial Relation studies by Kisaka (2010), Odhong, et. al., (2014), and Tubey (2015) provide critical information regarding the functions, effect, influence and interaction of employees and their unions. The studies also clearly point out the history and chronology of industrial relations in Kenya. In as much as, employee relations in Kenya are elaborate and it enjoys both legal and constitutional backing. The study on “An Overview of Industrial Relations in Kenya,” Tubey (2015), observes that industrial relations in Kenya enjoy both legal and constitutional backing. In addition, there are sufficient laws to regulate affairs in labour, though the industrial relations remain unstable hence a need for in depth investigation. Unions try to obtain a higher wage for their members than would be offered in the absence of union which, other factors constant results in in workers taking a greater share of profits at the expense of the firm. This monopoly face of unions tends to weaken management-employee relations where it leads to management adopting anti-union strategies, intensifying conflicts, while the union needs solidarity to monopolize power.

Odhong, et.al (2014; pp. 159-162)) in the study, “Re-thinking Industrial Relations for Enhanced Organization Performance in Kenya,” noted that the effect industrial relations are manifested in the increase in the spate of industrial strikes and attendant man-days lost. The study notes that the number of man-days lost due to industrial strikes almost doubled from 14,806 in 2008 to 20,504 man-days in 2010. The effect of strikes in terms of man-days lost, increased by sevenfold to about 175,329 in 2011. Other resultant effects of strikes include declining labour productivity in all sectors of the Country’s economy, increasing unit labour cost and low levels of competitiveness. Kenya’s labour productivity growth declined from 4 per cent in 2007 to 1.4 per cent in 2012.

The study by Kisaka (2010), it is not conclusive to adequately address performance without considering the effect of employee relations and industrial relations conclusively. The study further notes that an array of factor attribute the high levels of industrial disputes; among them is the current system and practice of industrial relations in Kenya which is designed for action to be taken only when industrial disputes erupts, parties to industrial relations disputes generally have weak negotiation skills, which dampen any prospects for speedy settlement of disputes. Data showed that the Country’s

production efficiency declined from 0.515 in 2008 to 0.588 in 2012. The worsening of the country's production and labour efficiency is rationalized on the grounds that industrial disputes disrupt the flow of production. It also causes mistrust, anxiety and lack of confidence. In addition, the non-cooperative nature of the parties and the weak management partnership aggravates mistrust and lack of confidence among parties to industrial disputes. This weakness, ostensibly manifest ineffective and lack of a proactive industrial relation system and practice. Conversely, the modern industrial relations system and practice require recognition of the dignity of the individual, respect to fundamental principles and rights at work inclusive of the right of the employees and trade unions to personal freedom and equality of opportunity, this entails including the employee view in decision-making (Odhong, 2014).

3.2 Employee Relations

The employee relations system in Kenya is anchored on the ILO Convention No. 150 of the Industrial of 178 on Labour Administration. This is domesticated through the Industrial Relations Charter (1984) and the Labour Relations Act (2007). The system provides for consultation between representatives of employees, employers and the government within a tripartite framework on issues affecting workers and employers, (Odhong, 2014). The Labour Law provides for the right of workers to form and join unions of choice. The trade unions are sector based, with a few general unions of Commercial, Food and Allied Workers that represents workers in varied sectors like banking, food, retail, and financial. Civil servants are also active members of worker organizations and exercise their rights (Labour Relation Act, 2017). According to the Kenya- Labour Market profile (2014), it is estimated that 1.9 million workers are members of trade unions, which covers a share of 11% of the labour force.

A study by A.H. Sequeira and Aproorva Dhriti (2015); 'Understanding Employee Relation Practices,' observed that employee relations involve maintaining a work environment that satisfies the needs of individual employees and management. The study focused on understanding employee relations practices, its underlying factors, issues and the resultant impact on employee performance. A descriptive research approach was adopted for the research to describe the existing employee relations practices, as well as a casual approach in order to link the employee relation factors to performance. The study revealed that the majority of employees of Kenya Systems had adequate resources provided mostly by private companies. As such, the provision of requisite resources positively impacted the employees' work and effectiveness. More so, employees with a higher level of job satisfaction in this case salary, work environment and growth opportunities were more productive at work, and were able to complete their work on time and were motivated to give an opinion for the organization's development and improvement of employees' performance.

According to Kanana (2016), employee relations management practices are employment laws, labour laws, concerted activity and collective bargaining. It involves communication between management and employees whereby the trade unions act as the intermediary between the employees and the employer when it comes to representing their grievances which mostly culminate in writing a collective bargaining agreement document. The study sought to determine the perceived relationship between employee relations management practices and job satisfaction at Swiss port Kenya Limited. The study utilized a descriptive research design. The study was guided by the Social Exchange Relation Theory by George Homan 1958, Abraham Maslow Hierarchy of Needs Theory and McClelland Needs/Achievement Theory.

The findings of the study showed that there is a high level of job satisfaction with respect to how disciplinary issues were handled. The study noted that that trade unionism in the organization also informed the level of satisfaction among the workers since it was an avenue of fostering communication and conflict resolution between the management band the employees. The success or failure of any organization is determined by its employees as they bare more valuable assets to combine the other resources such as finance, technology, information and production systems which enables the organization to achieve competitive advantage. This can only happen when employees work together, have an amiable relationship with their employees. Essentially, employee relationship management plays a critical role in the achievement of the organization's goals. Thus, it is apparent that a good relationship should be nurtured between the employees and their managers, as well as with the organization since it leads to increased productivity, staff motivation and high morale. Conversely, lack of dedication by employees' impacts negatively on the quality of services offered to customers (Hagos and Shimels, 2018). Essentially, creating a peaceful employee relation is a cardinal prerequisite if the goals and objectives of the organization are to be attained effectively and efficiently.

3.3. Employee Performance

Alusia (2016) studied, 'Factors Influencing Employee Performance in the Kenya Public Sector.' The purpose of the study was to assess the factors influencing employee performance in the Kenyan Public Sector. In an attempt to establish factors influencing employee performance, the researcher focused on recruitment and selection process, training and development and reward management as independent variables. The study population was 530 KeNHA employees countrywide; the sample size was 108 employees. The research however focused on staff working at the headquarter office. This study proposed important recommendations in the public service. Among these recommendations, is the importance of quality recruitment and selection planning; including assessing the need for employee recruitment; succession planning; quality of job description; influence of training and development on employee performance; career progression; efficient communication among employees; influence of job rotation on staff performance; induced motivation and enthusiasm in staff, and influence of reward management on employee performance. Nonetheless, the study suffers fundamental shortfalls: it cannot sufficiently be used for generalization purposes in the entire public sector since the sampled population captured mainly employees (mainly managers) stationed at the head office. Generally, staffs at the head office consist of policy and decision makers, who are responsible, for shaping the direction of the Ministry, Department or Agency. Obviously, there are no way officers at this level could provide the researcher with negative information or data which can implicate or used against their office, especially if it would paint the organization in a bad light. Worth noting, is the fact that the study was undertaken in a semi-autonomous sector, Kenya National Highway Authority (KeNHA); the public sector consists of Ministries, Departments and Agencies whose mandates and service delivery vary widely. Hence, there would be a fallacy of generalization to apply the findings of the study to the entire public sector. Kanana (2016) observes that human satisfaction is divergence. Social Exchange Relation Theory by George Homans 1958, Abraham Maslow Hierarchy of Needs Theory and McClelland Needs/Achievement Theory attests to that fact. It follows then, that what satisfies one person may not necessarily satisfy another. The divergence is even broadened given that different agencies and departments don't reward their employees equally or equitably. The remuneration and reward structure the researcher finds unsatisfactory, would be considered quite motivating if paid to employees with similar qualifications as employees of KeNHA, but working for a different Ministry or department in the Public Service.

The study observes that most employees believe that their promotion depends on the quality of the service they offer, whereas the majority of staff were looking forward to working longer for KeNHA, whether they are promoted or otherwise, whether their basic salary is increased or not. The researcher also asserts that most employees are not satisfied that their salaries are commensurate to their skills, work they do, and their level of expertise. This is obviously, is a contradiction in principle and practice. The study contradicts itself on the subject of reward management, when the researcher observes that most staff acknowledges that they are always appreciated for good performance and they are psyched to excel in their performance. In addition, the researcher observes that KeNHA's reward system has enabled workers to handle even the preconceived challenging projects and tasks, to the extent of building their work and career ambitions. It is not consistent and logical that at the same time, the study observes, that the majority of staff disagree that KeNHA promotes staff who excel before the maturity of the usual promotion period, as a source demotivation. Seemingly, the framing of the questions was not clear or objective as it ought to be. Recommendation to promote before the maturity of the set period contravenes the principles of consistency, fairness when rewarding employees.

Kimeu (2015) studied 'Perceived factors affecting employee performance at Machakos County Government.' The study was grounded on the **attribution theory**, which underpins and explains how people explain things (Weiner, 1985). A descriptive research design was used. A population of 1,300 employees was obtained from the Human Resource (HR) department. The results of the study revealed that appraisals affected employee performance with a mean of 4.2 out of 5. Other factors that affected employee performance included training, team work, and motivation. For instance, Employee Training is associated with higher levels of performance, while lack of Employee Training leads to lower levels of performance. The higher level of team work leads to a higher level of employee performance, and performance appraisal leads to higher performance. Despite the fact that the study captured the subject of perception of employees working at healthcare facilities, level 3 and 4 at Machakos, the study was limited in terms of the sampled population. For this reason, the recommendations of the study cannot generalize to other public healthcare facilities in the County. Furthermore, his studies are limited in the sense that it did not study healthcare facilities under the Machakos County Government who dynamics as not similar to that of levels 4, and 5.

Fundamentally, the study could have been a cross sectional survey, hence cluster the healthcare facilities, for example in categories in terms of urban, rural; located in densely populated areas or scarcely populated; or resourcing and facilitation of various facilities and human capital deployment. More so, glaring is the fact that healthcare is a system

hence one cannot dissect and handle a section and ignore the rest. The study only captured training, performance appraisal, motivation, and the team works as factors affecting employee performance. Simply put, one healthcare service affects the next level, that is why you cannot effectively conclude on the subject of employee perception without looking at the entire system and also external factors that affect job delivery by healthcare workers. For example, the issue of remuneration, work environment, and leadership cannot be separated from factors responsible for influencing employee perception of performance.

The previous studies did not look at the multiplicity of these factors. For instance, the question of unions and organizational productivity has received considerable debate on how the later affects the former. Trade unions have an impact on organizational productivity since they affect the stability and profitability of labour relation (Jepkorir, 2014). Though, performance appraisal has the ability to motivate an employee, it is only possible when the organization adopts a performance –based pay structure, when the appraisal system is SMART and supported fully by management. The appraisal should be aimed to strengthen the worker's weakness but not punitive.

Performance appraisal systems are criticized as focusing on management usage of appraisals to deal with employees' weaknesses rather than an improvement in employees' performance (Beach, 2005). As a matter of fact, according to the studies of Pareek and Rao (2006), where the main maim idea of appraisal was defined as supporting individuals in the process of training, development and motivation. That contradiction resulted in a significant divergence between rewards allocation based on evaluated performance and the past performance itself. Employees can only be motivated when the appraisal system provides a clear reward to those who perform exemplarily well and the reward should be fair, equitable, consistent and transparent, otherwise it can negatively affect employers to the extent of demotivating them instead of building their moral. In the same way, an appraisal system ought to be strategic in order to build formidable team work in the organization. This can be feasible when there is no bias and discrimination of any sort. According to Deb (2006) there is no single appraisal that can be the same for any chosen organization because of its variability based on environmental, cultural and organizational aspects. Newton and Findley's (1996) claim that occurred discrepancy leads employees up to unwillingness to reveal their draw backs, concerns, and undesirable working moments to diminish the negative consequences of possible promotions, pay increase, awards etc.

3.4 Salaries and Remuneration Commission (SRC)

3.4.1 Mandate and Functions of SRC

Salaries and Remuneration Commission (SRC) was established by The Constitution 2010; under Article 230 with the mandate to set and regularly review the remuneration and benefits of all state officers, and advise the National and County Governments on the remuneration and benefits of all other public officers. The commission was formed to set the desired levels of salaries and wages for civil servants in the country (SRC Act, 2011).

3.4.2. Principle of Pay Determination

The SRC was constituted at a time when Kenya's economy is experiencing recovery from the economic doldrums encountered in 2008 when the Country's GDP growth was as low as 1.5 % down from 7.0% in 2007. The GDP growth picked up from 2009, reaching 4.4% in 2011 with growth projected at over 5.6% for 2012. The GDP in 2018 stood at \$87,908 million. The absolute GDP was \$8,696 million with respect to 2017. The GDP per capita of Kenya was \$1,711, \$134 higher than in 2007 when it stood at \$1,577. Based on the economic situation, SRC is compelled the constitution to ensure fiscal sustainability; attraction and retention of requisite skills, recognizing productivity and performance; transparency and fairness; and equal remuneration to persons for work of equal value, (Section 12 (1) of SRC Act, 2011).

Despite the humongous mandate handed to SRC by the constitution, to regulate and harmonize salaries and wages paid to workers, employee unions and workers feel SRC is palaver and disregards CBAs arrived at after long and comprehensive negotiations and hinders their implementation, hence has rocked the industrial peace. Fail to implement or complete disregard CBAs has seen a surge of industrial action in the Country. Employees feel SRC has failed on her mandate including, to harmonize salaries and wages among employees within the same line of duty, improving their remuneration based on the prevailing economic situation hence should be disbanded as proposed by Kenya National Union of Teachers, University Academic Staff Union, and Parliamentary Service Commission. The SRC should be proactive and adopt a collaborative and consultative approach before making her far reaching decisions, and be seen to implement the mandate

and principles of remuneration to regain public confidence. Otherwise since the commission came into existence, it has not satisfied the expectation of the labour actors and gained the confidence of workers other than being seen as contemptuous to workers.

3.4.3 Wage Bill

According to the Institute of Economic Affairs report of 2014, Kenya has a total workforce of twelve (12) million, ten (10) million of whom are in the informal sector. The remaining two (2) million make up the formal sector which consists of the government civil service jobs; parastatals as well as the private sector. It is estimated that Kenya has a civil service workforce of about 700,000. This workforce is said to be the largest among Sub-Saharan Countries that are relatively at the same economic growth as Kenya. Consequently, this has led sky rocketing wage bill as opposed to raising reciprocal amounts of revenue. According to the report, the country's wage started soaring in 2008 following the formation of the Coalition Government in April 2008, as well as increased employment of public service officials, mostly teachers and nurses. Consequently, the push for a pay rise by unions for members has been in motion. Other causes of soaring wage bills are the hiring of new officers. The increased civil servants in the County governments in addition to those adopted from the defunct local governments. The new governance structure has seen the creation of a two-tier system of governance in the country. The number of Members of Parliament has increased, new positions of governor, senator, and county representatives created. The deployment of civil servants from the national government while county governments engaged in employment spree has greatly increased the wage bill.

4.0 Conclusions and Recommendation

4.1 Conclusion

Organizational productivity does not occur on its own or in a vacuum, in fact, there can never be organizational productivity without people (Amah & Ahiauzu, 2013). Performance management of employees is complex and integrated of setting up an understanding of targets by employees to be attained by the organization and aligning it with the human capital in the organization. Optimizing employee performance is critical for the public sector to win the confidence of the general public. At the same time, employer –employee relations cannot be ignored if workers have to deliver. The interaction of the employer and the worker's unions plays a role in ensuring industrial peace. Unions shape and influence the remuneration and working conditions of the works. Essentially, employee relations should be cordial if employee performance can be harnessed. The success or failure of any organization is determined by its employees as they are more valuable assets that combine with other resources such as technology, finance, information and production systems to enhance an organization's competitive advantage and sustain the organization's growth. Employee performance will depend upon job satisfaction, remuneration, reward management, promotion, motivation, favorable working environment, training and development, career development and succession. In addition, modern tools, sophisticated technology utilized by the organization for employee relations give an organization an edge over others.

4.2 Recommendations

- 1) The previous salary reviews for public service were not based on a systematic review method. There is a need to conduct salary adjustments based on a periodic and systematic based on the prevailing economic condition in cognizance of the principles of remuneration of equity and fairness. Review of the Current Employment System and make Public Universities Autonomous. For instance, employees in the public or private should obey the rules of economics. Kenyan Universities need greater autonomy, a transparent and competitive process of selecting university leadership and a performance based pay system. To resolve the numerous problems confronting the public sector, for example universities, a cordial and collaborative relationship between the three stakeholders is paramount. Universities in Kenya should be made autonomous, creative and innovative to expand their capital base and be able to take care of their fiscal demands. The trade unions too, should improve their terms of service to their members. However, in a climate defined by militant faculty unions and inflexible administration and government, it's not possible to forge common ground to address institutional challenges. Finally, frequent and prolonged strikes are detrimental to the development of industrial labour relations in universities. Labour unions for academic staff were only revived in 2003, having been outlawed in 1979. Since then the relationship between the union and the state has been adversarial. The union has defied court orders to call off the strikes. The government has also failed to honour

agreements with unions concluded after protracted negotiations. These violations run counter to the development of good labour practices in universities.

- 2) There is a need for Constitutional Review, especially the amendment of Labour Laws (2007). Fundamentally, the constitution (Article 40), grants workers the right to participate in the industrial action, there is urgent need to relook at the labour laws and seek a balance between individual rights and the wide subject of the basic human rights, and the balance in the same constitution with grants citizens the right to quality services from government institutions. The conflicting laws and unclear responsibility complicate the implementation of Collective Bargaining Agreements in Kenya. The law on strikes should be reviewed to address industrial unrest in the country. SRC should embark on a fair determination of remuneration based on output.
- 3) The spirit of Collective Bargaining should be embraced at all the requisite processes of CBA negotiation, as from the initiation level, negotiation, signing, dispute registration, till the stage of effective and efficient implementation of the CBA in question. The doctor's strike is illustrative. It indicates the professional is underpaid and ironically those serving the country in Government hospitals are at a distinct disadvantage compared to their private sector counterparts. SRC should spearhead extensive sensitization and dialogue to enable a change of mindset and attitude of Kenyans. There is a serious urgency for a change of mind by Kenyans. It will not be possible to change systems and have them work unless there is a radical change in attitude and mind set.
- 4) The engagement of tripartite parties should not just focus on wages but also wade into other amicable and sustainable strategies. The unions should explore other opportunities available to them, for instance progressively and proactively guiding and taking control of workers' destiny by making employees independent and autonomy in their incomes than always looking at the employer. In the event of a dispute in the employee and labour relations, there is need for exploiting other Dispute Mechanisms (ADRs), which have proven to be effective over time so that industrial peace is maintained with the aim of ensuring job performance is not affected by disharmony because of strained relations between the employer and employee.
- 5) There is a need for a serious dialogue in the Country to critically address the whole subject of the wage bill. The 2010 Constitution created two levels of government; National and County. The county government excessively employed workers in disregard of the prevailing economic situation in the Country. The constitution created bicameral parliaments, Independent commission and other state offices; cumulatively these offices ultimately did not only escalate the wage bill, but also causes duplication of roles, and serious salary discrepancies in the civil service.
- 6) Unions should come to terms with the fact that strikes are losing their sting in the evolving fight for workers' rights. As such, unions may not enjoy the privilege that comes with the smooth implementation of CBAs. Union leaders must retreat, research, reflect and re-strategize to engage employers meaningfully. This because of the oversupply of young, educated and readily available human capital is likely to complicate the usual trade unions strike mentality. Most importantly, union strikes are no longer attracting mob psychology and public sympathy as before. Often, the time the public perceives the strikes as personal and egocentric by union leaders since their agitation for better terms does not always mean reciprocal with the employees out and customer satisfaction.

References

- i. Amah, E, & Ahiauzu, A. (2013). *Employee Involvement and organizational effectiveness*. *Journal of Management Development*, (3), 661 – 674. Doi: 10.1108/JMD-09-2010-0064
- ii. Aluvisia, H.K (2016). *Factors Influencing Employee Performance in the Kenyan Public Sector: A case of The Kenya National Highways Authority*. A Research Project Submitted Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for the award of the Degree of Masters of Arts in Project Planning and Management of the University of Nairobi, Nairobi
- iii. Armstrong, M. (2008). *Strategic Human Resource Management: A Guide to Action*. Philadelphia: Kogan Page Publisher
- iv. Beach, S.D. (2005). *New Directions in Performance Management*. In S.D. Beach (ed) *Managing Human Resources: Personnel Management in Transition*. Oxford. United Kingdom: Blackwell
- v. Betty, M.J. (2014). *The Effect of Trade Unions on Organizational Productivity in the Cement Manufacturing Industry in Nairobi*. . A Research Project Submitted Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for the award of Masters of Business Administration Degree, University of Nairobi.

- vi. B.Nagaraju, and Pooja, J. (2017). *Impact of Salary on Employee Performance Empirical Evidence From Public and Private Banks Karnataka. International Journal of Marketing Human Resource Management*, 8(4), pp. 43-51.
- vii. Christine, A., et.al. (2013). *Factors Affecting Performance of Trade Unions in Kenya. American Journal of Business and Management Vol. 2, No.2, 181-185 DOI:10.11634/216796061302331.*
- viii. *Factors Affecting Trade Unions in Kenya. (2013). American Journal of Business and Management Vol.2, No. 2; 181-185 DOI: 10.11634/2167606130231*
- ix. Hagos, Brhane and Shimels, Zewdie, (2018). *A Literature Review on Employee Relations on Improving Employee Performance. International Journal in Management and Social Science Vol.6 issue 4, April ISSN; 2321-1784: Impact Factor: 6.178 Journal Home page:http/ijmr.net.in*
- x. Magdalene Koki Muthoka (2016). *Influence of Employee Relations Practices on Organizational Performance of Public Healthcare Sector in Kenya. Doctor of Philosophy in Human Resource Management. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture & Technology*
- xi. Muthoka, M.K, (2016). *Influence of Employee Relations Practices on Organizational Performance of Public Healthcare Sector in Kenya. A thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Human Resource Management in Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology*
- xii. Mwangi, K. Patrick. (2014). *The Effect of Compensation on Employee Motivation: A Project Report Submitted to Chandaria School of Business in partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for Degree of Masters in Business Management Administration, United States International University Newton, T., & Findley, P (1996). The Performance of Appraisal. Human Resource Management Journal 6(3) 34-58*
- xiii. Ngui, K. (2014). *Effects of Human Resource Management Strategies on the “Performance Strategies on the Performance of Commercial Bank of Kenya”.* Retrieved ir.jkuat.ac.ke
- xiv. Pareek, U., & Rao, T. (2006). *Designing and Managing Human Resource Systems. Oxford, United Kingdom: IBM Publishing*
- xv. Republic of Kenya (2017). *The Employment and Labour Relations Court Act. Kenya Law Reports*
- xvi. Republic of Kenya (2017). *Economic Survey. Kenya National Bureau of Statistics*
- xvii. Republic of Kenya (2007). *Employment Act 2007. Nairobi; Government Printers*
- xviii. Republic of Kenya (2007). *“Labour Institutions Act 2007, Kenya Law Review Reports*
- xix. Republic of Kenya (2011). *“Salaries and Remuneration Commission Act. Nairobi; Government Printers*
- xx. Tubey, R, et. al. (2015). *An Overview of Industrial Relations in Kenya. Research on Humanities and Social Sciences ISSN (Paper) 2224-5766-ISSN (online) Vol.5. No.6*
- xxi. Odhong, E., (2014). *Re-thinking Industrial Relations for Enhanced Organizational Performance in Kenya: Proceedings of International Conference on Sustainable Research and Innovation, Vol. 5, 7th - 9th May.*
- xxii. Owidhi, G. O. (2017). *Central Organization of Trade Unions: An Economic Paper for Decision making in Trade Unions in Kenya*